

Evidence-Based Toxicology Manuscript Assessment Report

TEBT-2023-0001: A general-purpose protocol for facilitating standards compliance when planning systematic reviews

First round of peer review | 05 06 2023

Note about EBT’s manuscript assessment process: The EBT submission assessment process evaluates a submitted manuscript for demonstrating that enough scientific work has been done that the relevant community would consider it to be a unit of contribution to the scientific literature. We define a unit of contribution as any useful, valid piece of research. It need not be a large contribution, having positive results is irrelevant, and it may even be an example of where research has not gone to plan but from which useful lessons for the community can nonetheless be learned.

The first stage of assessment is Editorial Triage, where the Handling Editor assesses a submitted manuscript (“Working Paper”) for compliance with EBT’s minimum requirements for submissions. Working Papers judged as meeting EBT’s minimum requirements go to peer-review, where three or four reviewers provide comments about what they think could be done with the manuscript, to make it the best contribution to the literature that it can be. These comments are aggregated by the Handling Editor into an Assessment Report (this document).

The authors, reviewers, and Handling Editor then discuss this report and attempt to come to consensus on the most appropriate way to modify the Working Paper, through a combination of one or more of additional experimental work, reanalysis of data, revisions to how the research is described, and qualification of the limitations of the research. If necessary, a revised submission is re-reviewed, further discussions held, and changes made, until the Handling Editor, authors, and peer-reviewers are satisfied that enough work has been done for the Working Paper to count as an Accepted Contribution. At this point the version of record of the Working Paper is formally published in the journal.

The structure of this assessment report is derived from the reviewer and author guidelines for Registered Reports (Chambers et al. 2023, <https://osf.io/pukzy>).

Manuscript title	A general-purpose protocol for facilitating standards compliance when planning systematic reviews
Preprint DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7521844
Submission Type	Single-stage study
Report authors	Olwenn V Martin (ORCID: 0000-0003-2724-7882), EBT Journal Handling Editor Iva Sovadinova (ORCID: 0000-0003-0627-243X), RECETOX Kerry Dwan (ORCID: 0000-0001-6918-1215), Cochrane UK Monica Gonzalez-Marquez and Ines Schmahl, Forschungszentrum Jülich
Recommendation	[enter brief summary of the recommendation to the authors]
Explanation	[enter an “executive summary” of the recommended changes and reasons for them]

Summary of reviewer comments

This manuscript is a proof-of-concept study aiming to set the initial groundwork to test the hypothesis that compliance with systematic review (SR) conduct standards and reporting checklists can be improved by reducing the amount of experience required for successfully using such standards and checklists. The authors developed code and a template for automated creation of a draft protocol manuscript. This allowed them to develop a theoretical understanding of how such a system may improve compliance with research conduct and reporting standards. They identified specific and general issues that would need to be addressed to enable further development and testing of the proposed approach.

Importance of impact of limitations on study findings	A limitation of the study is that it is not clear who its intended audience is
Potential additional work to overcome limitations	[Summarise the tendency of the reviewers toward recommending additional experimental work, analysis, and/or revision to address the limitations]
Potential acceptability of characterising limitations instead of doing additional work	[Summarise the tendency of the reviewers toward characterising the limitations of the study]

Structured assessment

1. Are the research questions or knowledge goals important?

<input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Neither agree nor disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat agree	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Strongly agree
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Comments: There is general consensus that the work is needed and of interest to the systematic review community.

Reviewer 1: The topic is both necessary and pertinent.

Reviewer 2: This is definitely of interest to the systematic review community but needs to be simplified somehow and considerations given to matters stated therein.

Reviewer 3: This is needed work.

Suggestions for addressing the comments: None necessary

2. Do the authors present a logical, rational, and/or plausible approach to achieving their research goals?

<input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat disagree	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Neither agree nor disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat agree	<input type="checkbox"/> Strongly agree
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Comments: There may be some confusion regarding the aims and scope of the work described in this manuscript. Although the longer term aim is to test the hypothesis that the

automated creation of a draft systematic review protocol may improve compliance with conduct and reporting standards, the aims of this proof of concept do not extend to actually testing that hypothesis. The aims of the proof-of-concept could be made clearer. Reviewers felt that the approach could also be clarified by characterising the experience and understanding that may be required of novice users of such a tool as well as the background information and guidance that would need to be provided alongside the automated tool.

Reviewer 2: There isn't much detail on the experience required for authors to undertake a review. There are concerns by the community that having a protocol template could allow authors to use this without actually knowing what they are doing and understanding the methods included.

Reviewer 3: Our concerns are that tool like this should make clear for whom they are intended, and that if intended for novices, then full examples should be provided along with definitions and explanations for all relevant concepts.

The manuscript's primary issue is that it isn't clear who its audience is. It often reads as if it were about to introduce conducting a systematic review to a novice but then the needed background information is not provided and key terms are either not defined or not described in enough depth, making the tool better suited for experts who want to simplify a process they are already quite familiar with. Our sense is that the authors intend for this tool to be useful to novices. If so, much more background information will need to be provided, beginning with what a systematic review is, what one is used for, and how it differs from a routine literature review. Also, the examples that are provided are disconnected. We're not sure if we misunderstood them and they do form part of a single example but we think not. For learners to truly understand a new process, it's very important that a complete example, no matter how simple, be provided from beginning to end. Each step must be described carefully, with all new terms defined.

Our recommendation is that the paper be reformulated as a guide to conducting SRs from beginning to end using the tool described here to ensure proper compliance, i.e. this is how you conduct an SR from start to finish and why (very important to clarify why things are done in given ways. Such a guide will then be extremely useful not only to novices, but also to e.g. instructors at libraries who are often tasked with teaching these kinds of skills. As such, a complete example with real information, even if it consists of a toy question, will also be invaluable. The key is that the different bits of documentation should have clear connections to each other so that learners can see and understand clearly how the different types of information in an SR map to each other. This is not clear in the example included in this version of the tool.

Suggestions for addressing the comments:

There is a need to clarify the intended audience for the current proof-of-concept, i.e. is the current proof-of-concept of interest for developers and experienced systematic reviewers, or presenting a tool ready to be used by novices? This represents editorial changes to improve the clarity of the aims and scope of the work presented, likely feasible and acceptable to the authors.

If the tool introduced in this manuscript were already intended to be "an explicit, step-by-step sequence of operational procedures", further analysis and experimental work may be necessary to ensure the usability of the tool for novice users, e.g. develop background information defining key terms as well as guidance and fully worked example. This

represents considerable additional work, may require additional funding and authors may select to instead clarify the aims of the current proof-of-concept template.

3. Is the methodology and/or analysis pipeline sound (including, if relevant, appropriate characterisation of its statistical power)?

<input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Somewhat disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Neither agree nor disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat agree	<input type="checkbox"/> Strongly agree
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Comments: There were no specific comment about the methods described to develop the general-purpose protocol. Reviewers identified the lack of user testing, either from SR specialists or novice users, as a major limitation of the work.

Reviewer 1:

1. While I recognize that this is a proof-of-concept project, I feel that feedback from users and systematic review writers who were not involved in the development of the protocol would be beneficial. Have the authors conducted any pilot testing and received feedback from users?
2. Furthermore, to be effective and widely adopted by systematic review writers, the protocol should be user-friendly and easy to understand. It would be helpful to know if there is any training available or planned for the use of this protocol.

Reviewer 2: There has been no user testing so it is difficult to know if this is a practical option.

Suggestions for addressing the comments: The lack of user testing has been highlighted as a major limitation to the work by several reviewers. The authors identify that a number of modifications and improvements may be necessary before the tool can be user-tested. Depending on capacity and funding, the authors may choose to conduct user-testing before publication of this manuscript but this is likely to entail considerable further work.

An alternative, as described in response to question 2 is to disambiguate the longer term goal and hypothesis that act as justification for this preliminary work from the specific aims of developing a proof-of-concept tool.

4. Are the methods detailed and clear, with sufficient raw data and code to provide for transparency and potential reproducibility?

<input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat disagree	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Neither agree nor disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat agree	<input type="checkbox"/> Strongly agree
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Comments: There were no specific comments on methods or code. However, the readability of the manuscript and accessibility to a wider audience may be improved if language associated with development of software or automated tools was briefly explained and clarified.

Reviewer 2: The manuscript was difficult to read. In order to make it more useful, the language and layout should be considered again as to where it could be improved to make it easier to read.

Suggestions for addressing the comments: There were no changes to the methods for development of the tool suggested, only that the language used be clarified to increase the readability of the work and its acceptability to its intended audience. This represent non-negligible editorial changes but should be feasible and acceptable to the authors.

5. Are the authors' findings and conclusions justified given their data and methodological processes?

<input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat disagree	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Neither agree nor disagree	<input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat agree	<input type="checkbox"/> Strongly agree
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Comments: There were no additional comments related specifically to findings and conclusions.

Suggestions for addressing the comments: No further suggestions.

Other comments

Reviewer 1:

- 1.1. The authors should provide the spelled-out version and the abbreviated form of any acronyms or abbreviations the first time they are used in the text. For instance, in the first paragraph of the Materials and Methods section (P4), "PW" is abbreviated and in line two of page six, "API" is abbreviated without being spelled out first.
- 1.2. The reference manager mentioned in Figure 3 is "Zotero", not "Ednote 20" – P7/L6.